

After blotting, the NM was immersed in either PAb or MAb, diluted 500× with blocking solution, incubated for 60 min, rinsed once with distilled water and washed twice with blocking solution (10 min each with gentle shaking).

Enzyme-labeled second antibodies, diluted 2000× with conjugate buffer [(CB), 0.01 M Tris-HCl, 0.1 M NaCl, 0.0005 M MgCl₂, pH 9.5], were incubated with each set of NM (one NM per antibody combination) for 60 min, and rinsed once with distilled water and twice with CB. For alkaline phosphatase, each set of NM was immersed in freshly prepared color development solution, each milliliter containing 0.33 mg nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT, grade III, Sigma) and 0.17 mg 5-bromo-4 chloro-3 indolyl phosphate -toluidine salt (BCIP, Sigma) and incubated in the dark for 2-4 h. For horseradish peroxidase conjugates, the blots were incubated in TBS containing 0.5 mg 4-chloro-1-naphthol/ml, 0.015% hydrogen peroxide for 15 min. Color reaction was stopped by washing each set in 0.01 M Tris-HCl containing 0.05 M EDTA, pH 7.5.

Violet color indicated the presence of GSV antigen.

MAb/GAM IgG : AP was the most effective antibody combination in detecting GSV in infected sap. Positive reactions were distinct and no detectable nonspecific reactions were seen in healthy plant extracts (see figure). High nonspecific reactions were found in the two other antibody combinations. With MAb/GAM IgG : AP, GSV was

Reaction of GSV-infected (dark spots) and healthy (open circles) sap to GSV-MAb using GAM IgG:AP as second antibody in dot-blot immunoassay.

detectable in as little as 2.5 µl sap of 10× dilution.

The principles of DBI and enzyme-

linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) are almost the same, but DBI assay is simpler and faster. □

Survival of stem rot (SR) fungi

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Rice SR caused by *Sclerotium* spp. like *S. oryzae* and *S. hydrophyllum* is common in Haryana. It survives from season to season through sclerotia that either remain inside the stubble or get mixed in the soil. The disease appears at maximum tillering in Aug.

1. Survival of *Sclerotium oryzae* in laboratory and field. Haryana, India.

We studied SR fungi survival from Nov to Aug in the laboratory and in the field. Infected tissues of both fungi were collected from the field. One set was chopped into small pieces (intact sclerotia) and kept in the laboratory at room temperature or buried 2 cm deep in the field. In another set, sclerotia produced on rice grain-husk medium (free sclerotia) were dried in the shade and stored in laboratory or buried in the field.

Monthly collections of sclerotia were surface sterilized with 0.05% HgCl₂, plated on 2% water-agar amended with 1,000 ppm streptopenicillin, and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C. Each treatment was run with 20 sclerotia 3 times. Sclerotial viability after 3- and 14-d incubation was recorded separately for *S. hydrophyllum* and *S. oryzae*.

Under laboratory conditions, more than 55% of the sclerotia of both fungi remained viable in Aug. Under field conditions, 20% of *S. oryzae* sclerotia and 33% of *S. hydrophyllum* sclerotia were viable. Intact sclerotia had higher survival than free sclerotia (Fig. 1, 2).

2. Survival of *Sclerotium hydrophyllum* in laboratory and field. Haryana, India.

Effect of cytozyme on incidence of rice sheath blight (ShB)

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Cytozyme containing a series of biologically active compounds may help increase plant growth and alter susceptibility to disease. We studied the effect of a cytozyme root dip on incidence of ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn [*Thanatephorus cucumeris*

Table 1. Effect of cytozyme and *T. viride* on ShB incidence. Assam, India, 1982.

Treatment	Sheaths infected 1.5 mo after treatment (%)	Infection ^a	
		After 1.5 mo	After 2.5 mo
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> alone	75.80	8.3	8.7
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> with 5 min cytozyme dip	43.49	5.0	6.7
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> with 2 h cytozyme dip	52.91	6.3	8.0
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> + <i>T. viride</i>	13.30	0.3	0.7
LSD (0.05)	16.37		
CV (%)	18.74		

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

(Frank) Donk = *T. sasakii* (Shirai) Tu and Kimbrough] in winter rice in 1982 and 1983. The effect of cytozyme on populations of *Trichoderma viride* Pers.

ex S.F. Gray, a known antagonist of *R. solani*, also was evaluated in the 1983 experiment. There were four treatments, each represented by four pots (Table 1).